

Designing an Entrepreneurial Marketing Model with the Approach of Developing the Country's Rural Products Market Share

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Abstract: The sale of products is known as one of the concerns of producers and suppliers of rural products. Considering the share of products produced in rural businesses in the market and the concerns of selling these products, it should be stated that these businesses need innovative and entrepreneurial methods for marketing their products. According to some experts, marketing is one of the necessities of the rural production system, whose importance is very evident in the process of rural production, and marketing is a very important category in the success of these businesses. The aim of the current research is to design an entrepreneurial model of marketing with the approach of developing the market share of the country's rural products. This is an applied research in terms of purpose and exploratory in terms of data collection method. The semi-structured interview, focus group and grouping of experts were used in the qualitative part, and structural equations and SmartPLS software were used in the quantitative part. Therefore, the components of rural businesses were first identified and proposed as a model and tested in a quantitative stage. The research results show that the proposed model has 5 dimensions such as entrepreneurship, internal drivers, external marketing drivers, market environmental conditions and contextual development. In order to present the entrepreneurial model of marketing with the approach of market share development, it is necessary for every business to carry out updated and optimal strategic planning at all levels, after knowing its current situation, based on the dimensions, components and indicators of the current model; it could be helpful to strengthen optimum communication with stakeholders, especially the industry, considering the role of rural settlements by developing a support structure.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Marketing, Market Share Development, Rural Businesses

I. Introduction

According to the statistics published by the Economic Accounts Office of the Iranian Statistics Center and the country's Rural Development Deputy, we have seen a decrease in the population of villages in recent years [15]. The governance of agricultural activities in the rural economy has created a structure that makes the rural economy suffer from certain problems, such as less flexibility in the face of short-term weather fluctuations, product price fluctuations at the time of harvest, product marketing, marketing restrictions, and users' dependence on the external environment and foreign markets, and the instability of income sources[8]. Villages have a large part of the population and production resources, especially water and soil, and play a significant role in the economic development and growth of the country[45]. Rural markets are guided by trust, loyalty and sensitivity to price [32]. Today, business scientists believe that paying attention to rural settlements is a safe and entrepreneurial platform for creating value and commercializing ideas. It has very beneficial effects in creating economic, social, and cultural value [28]. Rural settlements have always influenced by changes over time, which were affected by the location and the way of interaction or internal communication [25]. Rural markets are defined as parts of the overall market of any economy that have changed dramatically over the past decade. A decade ago, the rural market was unstructured and not the target of prioritizing companies. There was no innovative strategy and advertising campaign, there was the distribution system, but it was

weak. Lack of literacy and technology were other factors that led to poor access to products and low level of awareness among villagers [30].

Gradually, the demand in rural areas increased. Marketers in rural marketing can withstand various competitive pressures that depend on the strength of the companies. The views of farmers and traders about the important market strengths in rural marketing are availability of products and raw materials, government support, provision of communication facilities, pristine market, local support, marketing capacity, marketing knowledge and market surplus [34]. It can be clearly seen that one of the factors affecting the underdevelopment of economic enterprises in the country in terms of competitiveness in international arenas is the existence of problems in terms of scientific and practical development of marketing in economic enterprises [17,13]. The desire to gain more market share in a competitive environment forces people to make more efforts to use limited resources. This issue creates motivation in the market to find more growth opportunities by gaining more market share, which ultimately leads to the improvement of their performance [2,20]. The main directions include ensuring the sustainable development of rural households in the economic crisis, optimizing the use of rural households' resources, reducing the use of non-renewable resources, ensuring sustainable income for the rural population, the use of the power of family, and social agriculture [22].

In the era of globalization, only cultures that have the power of exchange and interaction may survive, cultures that can participate in building the human life of the global community, have something to be loved by others and their satisfaction as authentic human need [23].

Marketing is one of the most important pillars of any business, but marketing in the usual ways is not the answer to the chaotic business environment that is associated with risk and uncertainty. Many researchers have looked at marketing from the perspective of entrepreneurship [12]. There is a significant difference in the standard of living, tastes and preferences of rural and urban consumers. In rural products marketing, we need to understand the dynamics of rural and urban consumers. Growth in rural areas even during the COVID-19 pandemic highlights the huge potential of this sector as a demand center [44].

Marketers should develop their relationship with rural consumers and then develop and sell products based on their needs and demands. Development of rural markets is a way to develop the country. Companies should focus on rural markets and adopt new innovative strategies to utilize the untapped rural markets for their long-term survival and rapid growth in the market. Despite various challenges, rural markets always promise more growth for companies [43].

Many researchers and experts put special emphasis on entrepreneurial marketing and consider it one of the most important factors determining the survival of businesses [9]. Researchers agree that marketing in rural areas is different from urban areas. This is because rural areas have more limited resources such as marketing knowledge and marketing capabilities. Therefore, traditional marketing theory does not provide an adequate explanation of marketing. Entrepreneurial marketing is developed as marketing with limited resources [40].

On the other hand, entrepreneurial marketing is a relatively young and very dynamic research field; despite extensive research, it has not yet been sufficiently investigated due to the specific characteristics of today's world, including rapid changes and developments, increased complexity, increased competition, and the weakness of traditional methods such as planning. Strategic research, market forecasts, attention to new methods are necessary to overcome these changes. In this regard, entrepreneurial marketing is one of the methods that today's organizations have focused on it [19]. Entrepreneurship highlights how to create the right environment for your business and use your real resources and relationships to a limited extent [11].

The latest efforts to demonstrate the pure concept of rural entrepreneurship are related to value creation [35]. Entrepreneurship helps villagers in identifying new opportunities, innovation and creativity in activities and in fact optimal use of village resources in order to develop market share [41]. Considering the current turbulent business environment, business owners do not get a good share of the market with conventional methods, and the need for innovative and entrepreneurial methods is strongly felt in the market [31].

Entrepreneurial marketing is used to describe the process of marketing that seeks opportunities in unknown market events with limited resources [29]. Instead of prioritizing the concept of marketing in general, entrepreneurial marketing prioritizes an "influencer tactic" in satisfying unique needs, in which entrepreneurs identify, explore, and exploit opportunities that lead to strategic decisions. It is customer-oriented [41]. It can connect customers like a family, and it is considered less costly and innovative in marketing implementation [38].

Rural marketing broadly includes reaching customers, understanding their demands, offering goods and services, and finally satisfying consumers, which leads to more sales. The general perception is that only agricultural inputs such as seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, cattle feed and agricultural machinery have the potential to grow in the rural market. However, the rural market is growing with multiple growth compared to the city. In order to gain a competitive advantage, villages use their resources to improve their relative position compared to their competitors; improving their

position will lead to the formation of better opportunities in the future in the studies of market share and its growth, which are known as important performance indicators. It also creates a significant relationship between market share and economic profit.

The growth and even survival of most economic activities depends on the issue of market share. Therefore, they try to control the market optimally by predicting the market share as accurately as possible and planning correctly to guide the customers, and for proper planning, as one of the tasks, it is necessary to predict the events of future. Market participants use their resources with the aim of gaining competitive advantages, in order to improve their position against competitors by taking into account the market share in explaining the position of profitability and improving performance, due to the different structures of the market, they show contradictory results. Among the economic markets, the labor market is the most important market, as the economic situation of each region can be analyzed based on it. For example, the labor market situation can be counted as the reasons for migration from rural areas to urban areas, for this reason, its recognition and evaluation is fundamentally important. On the other hand, although the phenomenon of rural marketing has a long history in the world, it is a new and challenging issue in our country, which has not received the serious attention of planners and relevant officials. This neglect and lack of attention has caused significant socio-economic damages to rural producers, in such a way that their sustainable development has faced a serious threat. Considering the declining statistics of the country's rural population and the importance of this part of the economy and its share in the GDP, special attention to this economic cornerstone can create value in different dimensions of the society.

Therefore, in this regard, the main question of the research is: what are the effective factors on the entrepreneurial model of marketing with the approach of developing market share, and what dimensions, components and indicators does it include?

II. Review of Literature

Entrepreneurial marketing: It's about a decade, the term entrepreneurship has played a prominent role in the scientific and economic literature of the world. But unfortunately, due to the use of the word work in the definition of this self-evident concept of entrepreneurship, it has been only summarized in creating employment [3]. Entrepreneurship denotes recognizing and taking advantage of opportunities previously [36]. unrecognized as opportunities. It is the process of eagerly pursuing opportunities in order to create value for the customer through innovation, creativity, immersion in the market, networking, and flexibility. Entrepreneurial marketing is the interface between entrepreneurship and marketing; it reflects entrepreneurial behavior in the marketing methods of a company, by which innovation can be applied in market activities [1].

Market: Market is sometimes used as a place or a situation to determine the price, buying and selling, and trade and interact between the buyer and the seller [5]. Market share: includes the company's market position and its relative size. In other words, the company's sales amount can indicate the company's influence in the market and indirectly the reason for its reputation, recognition, distribution capabilities or even the real quality of the company. Basically, the company's sales amount indicates its size compared to other potential competitors, sectors or the whole market. Usually, there is an argument that the more market share a company has, the more successful that company is. The more the number of commercial competitors in the industry, the more the company has to compete with more companies in order to obtain the share of sales and financing, and to meet its needs [39].

Development of market share: For the first time, IgerEnsef explained the strategic direction for the growth of business unit activities by presenting a matrix in two dimensions of product and market [7]. Although Ansef considers only one case as market development, in some sources, product development and influence in the market are also considered to be the cause of the development of the existing market and it is called as market reform [21]. Ansef's matrix represents growth strategies in the organization and each of these strategies ultimately affects the development and market share of the organization. It is obvious that any factor that can change the size of the company and the market share can also change the structure of the market. Among the variables that affect the market share changes and the structural changes of the market, we can refer to the research and development costs, which are among the behavioral variables of the market [24].

Rural business: a small-scale business in villages with less than 20 employees and its main field of activity is agriculture, animal husbandry, medicinal plants and other things related to the village. Now rural development interacts with the phenomenon of entrepreneurship more than before. Institutions and personalities promoting rural development consider entrepreneurship as a strategic intervention that can accelerate the process of rural development. But it seems that they all agree on the need to expand rural economic enterprises [27].

III. Experimental Studies

Some studies that have been carried out in the field of entrepreneurial marketing model with the approach of developing the market share of rural products (in the field of herbal spirits and carpet weaving businesses) are as follow:

By studying various researches, it was observed that the combination of marketing and entrepreneurship can play an effective role in the development strategy, there is a significant relationship between the combination of person, price, and promotion [37]. Regarding the women's clothing in Zahedan, the dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing (innovation, customer orientation, risk-taking, creating value, being ahead of the curve) affect the small women's clothing businesses [6]. In fact, the effective factors of entrepreneurial marketing that can be effective in the research of Gharavi and Safarian[9] and Ahmadi et al. [1] include communication capability, strategy, support and systems used, capabilities and characteristics of the entrepreneur, team, commitment, value proposition, and presentation.

On the other hand, by studying entrepreneurial marketing models, it can be seen that the dimensions of entrepreneurship-oriented, market-oriented, customer-oriented, and innovation-oriented perspectives can play a role in the development of the market share of rural products [4]. In addition, the impact of value, search opportunities, resource organization, customer value creation and risk acceptance as well as the innovation system can be considered as a very important dimension in entrepreneurial marketing that can increase the performance of small businesses [27, 26, 16]. It can also be seen in past researches that rural views play an important role in the economy and contribute to national prosperity and well-being, but often a blind spot is observed in rural development and broader economic policies and evidence. Also, the development of tourism business space is very effective and efficient in order to achieve sustainable rural development. Economic, infrastructural, social and individual variables respectively have the highest regression effect on the development variable of rural entrepreneurship. According to the studies, the research shows the importance of tourism in the process of increasing employment and growth of entrepreneurship, and increasing the power of rural tourism leads to business prosperity and increasing entrepreneurship opportunities and employment growth in rural areas [10, 14, 18, 33].

The present research includes the activists in the field of herbal spirits products in selected villages of Kashan city, who have university education, the number of people working in their businesses is less than 20 people, and they have been active in this field for at least two years and have a product variety of more than 5 items. Regarding the reasons for choosing these villages, the first one is the abundance of rural businesses in the field of herbal spirits in the city (these nine villages are the best in the field of herbal products in Kashan). The second reason is the strong role of Isfahan province in the gross domestic product of the agricultural sector, as well as the undeniable role of Kashan city in the rural production of this province. In addition, on this basis, an original research was conducted by researchers in Kashan in 2018 and its results were also published (under the title of Paradise in the Desert).

IV. Methodology

The present research method is exploratory in nature; it is also an applied research in terms of purpose. In the current research, qualitative research method was used to identify the concepts and components of entrepreneurial marketing and the development of rural market share. In this approach, it considers people, their interactions, perceptions, meanings, and knowledge as the primary source of data, and the interview method is an acceptable technique to discover individual and collective understanding and knowledge of people. For this purpose, the qualitative method of focus groups is used.

Characteristics of the studied community in the qualitative stage:

- 1) Activists in the field of entrepreneurial marketing
- 2) Activists in the field of rural production in the country
- 3) Policymakers and executive managers to develop the share of rural products
- 4) Faculty members involved in marketing and entrepreneurship
- 5) Entrepreneurial Marketing Specialists

In the preliminary stage, 15 interviews and a focus group of 7 people were conducted in order to gain knowledge from the experts in this field. The process of the interviews was planned and designed in such a way that after each interview, the data was coded and analyzed so that while identifying the proposed dimensions by the primary experts, these dimensions could be followed up in the subsequent interviews. In the present research, it was found in the twelfth interview that the findings are repeated, and for more assurance, three more interviews were conducted. In the main phase of the qualitative research, which used the expert grouping method, 7 experts in the field of entrepreneurial marketing and rural market share development participated in the discussion of data grouping.

In the current research, a targeted approach was used to select the qualitative research sample and the snowball sampling method, which is a subset of sequential sampling, was used to identify and select experts. The data collection

method in the qualitative section covers content analysis and interviews. In the current research, according to the subject and research objectives, the semi-structured interview was used. The proposed research model is developed based on expert grouping and using MaxCuda software. In the quantitative part of the data analysis, descriptive and inferential statistics were used to examine the variables of the research, and in the analytical statistics of this research, the structural equation model was used to test the research hypotheses.

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The statistical population includes activists in the field of herbal spirits products in 9 villages of Kashan (Armak, Fin Bozorg, Aznavah, Warghan, Sar, Ravand, Mashhadhardhal, Hosseinabad and Kaleh) who have university education and have been active in this field for at least two years, which is 35 people. A sample of 32 villages was identified and selected using Cochran's formula (The reason for choosing these villages as a statistical community is the interview with the experts of this region and inquiries from the relevant institutions; on the other word, in these two areas, the most active villages of Kashan city have been selected as statistical population.

Table 1. Summary of the research method.

Validity & Reliability	Sample	Statistical Population	Levels of Research
Reliability with pear check method Validity using the field note method	Snowball	Interviews with experts mentioned in the text and stopping based on saturation of codes	Qualitative
Validity using CVR calculation Reliability using Cronbach's alpha	Cochran's formula	Activists in the field of perfumery products in 9 villages of Kashan who have university education and have been active in this field for at least two years.	Quantitative

V. Findings

In the first stage of qualitative research, content analysis and semi-structured interview method were used, according to the interview process, interviews were conducted with 15 people; then, a focus group process was conducted with 7 experts. In the following, the extracted indicators were grouped by the experts in order to create the model. In this part, qualitative data obtained from 15 semi-structured interviews and content analysis are analyzed, which is 571 codes. Considering that the goal was to design an entrepreneurial model of marketing with the approach of developing market share, the experts were asked to select the desired codes by studying 571 extracted codes. Therefore, more than 50% of experts chose 382 codes. In the next step, the experts were asked to put the codes that are of the same gender in a separate group so that central coding can be done in this research (7 experts in the focus group meeting and at the same time as the screening steps and determining the importance of each index). Therefore, after completing this stage of the meeting, the codes were grouped into 5 dimensions and 16 components by experts.

Figure 1. Proposed model to identify factors affecting the entrepreneurial model of marketing with the market share development approach.

Figure 2. Quantitative conceptual model of research.

Table 2. Expert grouping.

	Components	Dimension	Concepts
1	Opportunity Efficacy Innovation Education	Entrepreneurship	Entrepreneurial marketing with market share development approach
2	Driver Organizational Structure Funds Flexibility in offering products Marketing and Advertisement	Internal drivers	
3	Branding Rules Rural communication Rural products market Variety of products	External drivers of marketing	

4	Distribution and sales	Market environment
	Market quality	
5	Responding to local demand	Contextual development
	Strategy	
	Capacity Building	
	Rural capabilities	
	Appropriate production and distribution infrastructure	

Quantitative Hypotheses

- H1: Internal drivers have a significant effect on the entrepreneurship of village productions.
- H2: external drivers have a significant effect on the entrepreneurship of village productions.
- H3: Textile development has a significant effect on the entrepreneurship of village products.
- H4: Internal drivers have a significant effect on the environmental conditions of village production.
- H5: External drivers have a significant effect on the environmental conditions of village production.
- H6: Textile development has a significant effect on the environmental conditions of village productions.
- H7: Environmental conditions have a significant effect on the entrepreneurship of village productions.
- H8: Environmental conditions have a mediating effect on the relationship between internal and external drivers and contextual development on rural production entrepreneurship.

Model Validation and Testing

The validity of the theoretical model of the research and the calculation of the effect coefficients have been used using the structural equation modeling method. Smart Pls method has been used to fit and evaluate the validity of structural equation models.

Table 3. Cronbach's alpha criterion, composite reliability and convergent validity of hidden research variables.

Acceptance level	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Acceptance level	Reliability	Cronbach's alpha	Symbol	Variables
0.5	0.701	0.7	0.921	0.892	EN	Entrepreneurship
0.5	0.848	0.7	0.965	0.954	IS	Internal drivers
0.5	0.682	0.7	0.913	0.876	ES	External drivers of marketing
0.5	0.636	0.7	0.897	0.854	EC	Market environment
0.5	0.748	0.7	0.936	0.915	TD	Contextual development

According to the findings of the above table, these criteria have adopted an appropriate value for the variables, it can be confirmed that the reliability and validity of the research is appropriate.

The fit of the structural and overall research model shows that the overall research model is confirmed.

Table 4. Fit of the overall model.

Communalities	R ²	Q ² =1- SSE/SSO	Variables
0.701	0.918	0.629	Entrepreneurship
0.848	-	-	Internal drivers
0.682	-	-	External drivers of marketing
0.636	0.915	0.575	Market environment
0.748	-	-	Contextual development
0.722	0.916		Average
0.813	GOF		

Figure 3. Path coefficient of the research model.

Figure 4. T-statistics of the research model.

The size of the path coefficient indicates the strength of the relationship between two variables, and for the path coefficient to be significant, the t-statistic value of each path must be greater than 1.96. Sobel test and variance accounted for (VAF) have been used to check the mediation hypotheses. According to Figure 6 and 7, it can be said that all the hypotheses are confirmed according to the statistical reasoning, and for further study, refer to the appendices section.

The importance of the constituent variables does not have a significant difference, and its average shows the importance of each of the concepts in rural businesses, and in the final part, based on the importance, suggestions will be made to strengthen these concepts.

According to the results obtained from structural equation analysis, it can be concluded that the model designed from interviews and codes extracted from Max Coda can be used in rural businesses, as the 5 main dimensions that have been

analyzed according to the amount of GOF have a general fit. On the other hand, the questioned axes of these 5 dimensions, which are as follows, have been identified as the most important components in rural business.

Opportunity, self-efficacy, innovation, and training were developed in the form of entrepreneurship; driver, organizational structure, financial resources, and flexibility in offering products were developed in the form of internal drivers of entrepreneurship; advertising, branding, rural communication, rural product market and product diversity were applied in the form of external drivers; marketing and advertising, branding, rules, rural communication, rural product market and product diversity were directed in the form of market environmental conditions; distribution and sales, market quality and response to local demand were developed in the form of market environment conditions; strategy, capacity building, rural capabilities, appropriate production and distribution infrastructure were developed in the form of contextual development.

VI. Conclusion and Suggestions

In fact, the main purpose of creating the concept of entrepreneurial marketing was to achieve a proper understanding of the commonality of marketing and entrepreneurship disciplines and to understand the impact of entrepreneurial behavior on marketing and, in contrast, to adopt innovative approaches in marketing. It should also be stated that marketing and economic growth will increase the market share. Due to the traditional view of selling products and paying little attention to marketing, the villagers face limitations in marketing activities (which, of course, will be largely prevented through education), changes in customer tastes and market dynamics will also cause to deepen the gap between the current and the desired situation for the traditional performance.

While these industries play a central role in economic development and it is important to pay attention to their market development. The relations between the city and the countryside have increased in recent years with the aim of exploiting the rural environmental resources, which has caused the presence of citizens in rural areas and created new needs, and has brought about new economic activities in rural production. These activities play an important role in the economic development of rural areas. From the economic aspect, these activities have created new opportunities in the rural areas, which makes the development of the rural market share sustainable. Since environmental factors affect the tendency to entrepreneurship and environmental factors strengthen or weaken the influence of the tendency to entrepreneurship, to increase the level of entrepreneurship, factors such as the support of top managers, constructive communication, lack of concentration and formality, as well as cultural, economic, political factors and the values of the society should be considered. Institutions and personalities promoting rural development consider entrepreneurship as a strategic intervention that can accelerate the process of rural development. But it seems that they all agree on the need to expand rural economic enterprises. The comparative study conducted with the researches of other researchers shows that many of the factors obtained in previous researches are not mentioned and are considered among the new results of this article. In fact, this research cannot be compared with past researches, it was tried to use all the results of past researches in the field of entrepreneurial marketing and market share development in rural productions in coding.

The studies conducted by Allahdadi et al., Ahmadpourdariani, Esfahani et al., Imani et al., Hamidzadeh et al., Khakzadian et al., Sadiko et al.; Morrish and Jones, Jenson et al. and Philipsen et al. are only the small parts of the research used. In summary, the studies show that the 5 investigated factors affect rural businesses; environmental conditions can be considered as a mediating variable in the relationship between other factors, which is not unaffected.

According to the proposed model, suggestions have been made for all five main dimensions in order to strengthen rural businesses.

Renovation of damaged rural areas and development of job creation in the country's villages through the governance of the entrepreneurship space and the creation of entrepreneurship parks in centers and susceptible areas, as well as supporting rural graduates to start businesses in the villages.

Long-term strategies for the development of rural entrepreneurship include creating special conditions for reversing the migration process, reforming and changing the pattern of distribution and energy consumption, developing and optimizing transportation networks, banning the change of use of garden, agricultural and forest and pasture lands, improving management and reforming production methods in agricultural sectors, developing conversion industries, fastest growing industries in susceptible areas, economicization of agricultural and rural goods, universal access to preliminary education, promotion and improvement of class gaps and promotion of rural women's capabilities, improvement of health level, creation of fun and uplifting living environments, effective support for the formation and development of cooperatives and the creation and expansion of rural cooperative complexes, the formation of self-governing savings groups to provide part of the financial needs of entrepreneurial projects, reating small credit systems in order to provide facilities such as establishing a rural bank, creating integrated training centers in order to provide training and consulting services in various fields of marketing, caring for domestic animals, handicrafts and other

required skills, attracting businesses from other areas, maintaining and developing existing businesses through support policies and supporting the creation of new businesses from rural areas.

Preparing the social, cultural and economic environment of rural areas, including providing and increasing the access of villagers to various facilities and services, such as new media and communication facilities, can be very important in the emergence of entrepreneurship.

The training of those villagers who have even a little background for entrepreneurship is a priority. Because we cannot expect all rural people to be entrepreneurs.

Completing and developing the country's rural information society, such as establishing telecommunications, improving their information literacy, and bringing the oral culture of the villagers closer to the digital written culture.

Eco-oriented rural space is formed in line with the strategies of monitoring, self-sufficiency, resource efficiency, diversity and choice, attention to human needs, flexibility, pollution reduction, diagnosis and biological support, and it can be realized with physical, functional and semantic criteria as the components of the village location.

Responding to the needs of the residents, especially in terms of welfare, can be achieved by using the stimulus of tourism, and the arrival of tourists has led to the development of social infrastructure that the rural community will benefit from; using drivers such as cultural tourism, this approach is a way to revive and improve the quality of life in the village through the improvement and development of the special characteristics of the historical values and cultural attractions of the place. Also, rural tourism is considered as one of the transformational factors in rural areas, which can be used as an alternative solution to solve rural problems. In this regard, according to the needs of the citizens, some rural areas have been able to plan to meet the needs of the citizens.

Applying innovative strategies in marketing performance, which are: flexibility strategy in marketing approach, process modification and improvement strategy, customer focus strategy, marketing innovation coalition strategy, market focus strategy and differentiation and uniqueness strategy considering the importance of marketing for rural businesses, it is recommended to organize free consulting programs on proper marketing.

The existence of a term called driving in the market, in the sense of continuously evaluating the market environment and trying new methods to penetrate the market and not be limited to one market and to discover new markets in order to increase the growth rate of one's market share.

Using internal strategies such as innovation in value, increasing compatibility with the market, so that they are ready to be more present in the market, and focusing on the facilitating factors of entrepreneurial marketing and trying to institutionalize the dimensions of this type of marketing to effectiveness and efficiency, and finally lead to improved performance.

Changing the ruling attitude of managers and people towards the village through: creating culture through mass and public media, highlighting and paying special attention to rural areas in the education system, expressing special attention to villages by senior managers.

Budget indicators (resources spent to support market development) and performance measurement indicators (achievements of the market development plan) should be formulated and simultaneous analysis should be done to prevent deviations in market development.

Making the country's rural atmosphere attractive through: targeted development of cultural and educational spaces in villages, creation of recreation, accommodation, and tourism centers in villages.

The flourishing of the rural economy and the establishment of new villages that are comparable to the cities in terms of location and facilities, is the development of handicrafts and their modernization, the attraction of foreign investors and the private sector to the villages, and the creation of culture to change the patterns of consumption and production in the village. On the other hand, empowerment is one of the main pillars of rural management and development. It should be taken into account by increasing choice, expanding individual and group potential opportunities and capacities, democratic decision-making, and empowering people to make decisions for shaping and managing their own environment. They should expand their marketing capabilities by participating in the market development support plan and use this skill as a business development tool. The most important prerequisite for market development is legal capacity building. Paying attention to the development of the rural labor market and its convergence towards the development level of the urban labor market in Iran can be aligned with the goal of creating equal opportunities and appropriate distribution of income. Building trust is essential to attract maximum participation and continue market development activities.

Considering the limitations of the current research, it is worth mentioning that considering that this research was conducted in the field of herbal extracts and in the context of Kashan city, it will not be possible to generalize the current model to other fields. Also, considering that this research was conducted in 9 villages of Kashan city, future researchers are suggested to investigate this model in other areas and rural contexts. The authors of this article have declared their readiness to cooperate in the continuation of this study for other rural areas of the country and will welcome the

conclusions and opinions of future research.

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